

Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS

Development of a national energy system model – Activity 4

Please use the following citation for:

- **This Activity**

Plazas-Niño, F. (2024, April). Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Development of a national energy system model – Activity 4 (Version 1.0).

- **OSeMOSYS UI Software**

Climate Compatible Growth. (2024). MUIO (Version v5.0.0). GitHub. <https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/MUIO>

- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

If you are stuck, please ask questions [here](#). If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'OSeMOSYS UI' and not 'ClicSAND'.

Tasks

1. **Familiarizing Yourself with the Data-To-Deal Concept:** Read the following two documents explaining the concept of Data-To-Deal. This innovative approach has been successfully implemented in Costa Rica to secure concessionary finance based on open-source energy system modelling. These documents will be included in the theory assessed during Midterm II.

First document [\[link\]](#)

Second document [\[link\]](#)

2. **Advancing the writing of the research article:** To begin drafting the introduction section of the paper, we need to gather information about the energy context of our country. This includes exploring the national energy balance, domestic energy

production, energy imports and exports, sectoral energy consumption, and the evolution of greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, conduct a search for previous energy modelling studies pertaining to your country using keywords such as 'energy modelling in [your country name]' or 'energy system model in [your country name]'. Search engines like Scopus or Web of Science are recommended for comprehensive results. Afterward, please summarize the information for the energy context in 3 to 4 paragraphs and provide 2 to 3 paragraphs regarding the literature review. As an example, please read sections 1.1, and 1.2 in the following paper [[link](#)] for guidance.